

Original Article

The Water Wars: Weaponizing the Indus Waters Treaty

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Abstract

Water, being a limited commodity, is essential for human life, which establishes its importance for all nations. Due to its significance for human survival, every nation wants to control the water resources, making it a security issue around the globe. This study is looking at the water issue as a new weapon that is potentially more lethal and devastating for the survival of water-stressed nations. Based on the securitization and “hydro-hegemony”, the study is analyzing the patterns where climate change, dam constructions by upper riparian countries and political dynamics are shaping the power undercurrents among the river-sharing nations. The paper is focused on the Indus Basin, where India’s unilateral suspension of the Indus Waters Treaty, coupled with its threats to alter river flows, constitutes the weaponization of water against downstream Pakistan. Pakistan’s heavy dependence on the Indus and its vulnerability to climate impacts render such strategies potentially devastating. This conflict is situated within global discourse and legal mechanisms, ranging from Boutros Boutros-Ghali’s cautions to the United Nations Watercourses Convention and the Vienna Convention on Treaties. The study concludes that when water is securitized and weaponized, it can inflict significant slow-onset harm without necessarily triggering the conventional thresholds of war. Consequently, international legal frameworks and cooperative institutions must be strengthened promptly to ensure that, in contemporary times, shared waters serve as a binding force between nations rather than a tool of coercion

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Introduction

Fears of “water wars” have haunted the conversation around global security for decades (Starr, 1991) Political leaders were already sounding alarm bells over future water conflicts Egyptian diplomat and later UN Secretary-General; Boutros Boutros-Ghali famously claimed that “the next war in the Middle East will be fought over water” (Duarte & Gama,2025). The phrase water wars became more common since it was popularized with a 1991 World Bank report of the same name, which claimed that with the rise of population, temperature and deforestation all driven by water consumption the demand for water increased between 1940 and 1990 (World Bank, 1991). The title of the book and the report was never intended to be taken literally, but there has been no shortage of claims that describe water as the “new oil”. This followed publication of a book by then Vice President of the World Bank Ismail Serageldin *Imminent Water Crisis* in 1995 (Serageldin, 1996).

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In 1994, the Global International Waters Assessment released its first comprehensive assessment of the state of the world's international water resources. Such grim predictions cast H₂O as a potential cause of interstate war, just like land or ideology. The story is particularly poignant in South Asia, where rival nuclear-armed neighbors share the Indus River system, a vital lifeline already under intense strain from rising demand and climate change (The Times, 2025).

However, academic research presents a more nuanced perspective, often challenging the simplistic narrative of a “water war.” Empirical analysis of transboundary water relations since the mid-20th century reveals very few instances of violent conflicts directly over water (Wolf, 1998). In most cases, disputes over shared water resources have been settled through negotiation and institutional mechanisms rather than armed conflict. In the best of cases, shared scarcity can even lead to collaboration so long as effective treaties and governance regimes have been established (Zeitoun, & Mirumachi, 2008). This pattern indicates that even though water stress will make tensions worse, conflict was not necessarily predetermined. But the lack of a declared war does not mean there is no coercion. Water can and increasingly is used as a strategic tool below the threshold of war. States are securitizing concerns about water, depicting them as national security threats warranting extraordinary response (Warner & Boas, 2019). Indeed, strong headwater riparian commonly exploits their advantage to establish “hydro-hegemony” over weaker downstream disputants. Hydro-hegemony entails control over transboundary water through physical control of territory, military strength or economic power that enables one state to enforce its water will over other states in the river basin (Mustafa, 2010). We've seen this play out around the world from Ethiopia's upstream dam building efforts along the Nile to China's command of the Mekong headwaters and it is playing out in South Asia in the Indus Basin, where India is geographically positioned higher up, and it is Pakistan that finds itself downstream (Yihdego *et al.*, 2017). Most importantly, global trends are intensifying these imbalances in water-related power. Rising population pressures and unregulated consumption are pushing water demand beyond sustainable limits. This stress is further compounded by climate change, which is altering hydrological cycles, triggering more extreme droughts, floods, and accelerated glacier melting, thereby disrupting historical river flows. In regions already ridden with political tensions, these pressures manifest the conflicts (Kundzewicz & Krysanova, 2010). One of the important aspects of the modern state system is the incorporation of international law, to streamline the relations among nations effectively. In this context, international law has tried to regulate the use of water and its distribution through different conventions and agreements. Some of the important legal arrangements include the 1997 “United Nations Convention on the Non-Navigational Uses of International Watercourses”, a convention that aims to safeguard the equitable and reasonable use of rivers while preventing damage to the water body. The 1966 Helsinki Rules try to ensure cooperation in managing shared water resources (ILA, 1996). Although the nature of these laws, along with other bilateral treaties, is binding under international law, they ultimately depend on the discretion of the sovereign states (Dinar, 2008). Consequently, all such laws and treaties are prone to the whims of national political aspirations and may create a crisis at any time without any regard for international rules and regulations (Wolf et al., 2003).

Keeping the political vulnerability of the international norms, this article analyzes the Indus Waters Treaty (IWT) between India and Pakistan as a case study. It is argued that India's recent move to suspend the IWT unilaterally, a political move to restrict Pakistan's water supply, represents a significant example of weaponizing water, which could pose an existential threat to Pakistan without resorting to conventional war (Haar, T., 2025). In a region already burdened by historical disputes and nuclear tensions, the strategic use of water emerges as a novel form of coercion—less immediately destructive than nuclear warfare, yet capable of slowly destabilizing entire nations. The following subsections analyze this scenario through the lenses of water securitization and hydro-hegemony, situating it within the broader global discourse and the legal-political framework of the Indus Basin (The Tribune, 2025).

The aim is to shed light on how water could become a weapon and how it could destabilize regional peace and what international principles or mechanisms could help to prevent such a scenario (The Economic Times, 2025).

Literature Review

The Emergence of the Water Wars Discourse Early warnings of water wars, such as those issued by Boutros-Ghali, Bulloch, and Darwish, first drew widespread international attention to water and positioned water, or water scarcity, in the metaphor of the ‘oil of the 21st century’ in relation to conflict (Boutros, 1991). By the 1990s media and popular policy discourse was filled with scenarios of how rivers like the Nile, Jordan or Indus will be a cause for the next water war between states (Wolf, 1998). Such claims led to a securitization of water within the diplomatic discourse framing water scarcity as an existential threat to national security (Zeitoun, & Warner, 2006). In the Middle East, Israeli and Arab leaders spent many years sniping at each other about water rights (Selby, J, 2003), while in South Asia commentators now and then predicted that India and Pakistan’s next war would be fought over the Indus, rather than Kashmir (Shah *et al*, 2007). This self-securitizing narrative was echoed by influential figures such as the World Bank Vice President Ismail Serageldin, who in 1995 speculated that “the wars of the next century will be fought over water, not oil” (Serageldin, 1995). Such pronouncements have turned the water issues from the civic management and developmental domain to the security domain. These trends created a new security dilemma for states to strategize the, what we international relations scholars call, “water securitization.” (Allan, 2001). The securitization theory is clear about its importance in state affairs, as any issue when security becomes an important element of its national security, demanding immediate and drastic counter-measure to minimize the threat. Pakistan’s leadership, for instance, frequently emphasizes that reliable access to Indus River water is a cornerstone of national security, and any threat to the flow of these rivers is perceived as a threat to the nation’s very survival (Fischhendler, 2015). This rhetoric indicates that water has been fully securitized in Pakistan’s strategic thinking, a perception made even more pronounced by repeated warnings that an Indian water blockade would be considered an act of war (Mirumachi, 2015).

Nevertheless, to temper the alarmist narrative, considerable scholarly work has highlighted that water wars are far from inevitable. Research, notably by Aaron Wolf and colleagues, has analyzed hundreds of international water interactions and found that cooperation overwhelmingly outweighs conflict (Brochmann, 2012). One study note that between 1945 and 1999, states signed around 200 water-sharing treaties, with only a few disputes escalating militarily—and none resulting in full-scale war fought solely over water.

Many academics suggest that water resources could be a contributing cause of conflict, but not the single source: that institutions and policies have often managed the problem (Tir, 2012). Known as the “water peace” thesis, the idea is that common water incentives can provide incentives to cooperate, because all parties will ultimately suffer if rivers are not sustainably managed (Conca, 2002). The IWT itself is often used as evidence; amid three major wars between India and Pakistan, the terms of the treaty were for the most part adhered to, and the Permanent Indus Commission continued to function even during times of overt conflict. This in turn underscores the point that successful treaties can act as a deterrent to conflict, turning water from a potential *casus belli* into a source of cooperation (The Indus Waters Treaty, 2025). However, skeptics of the “water peace” thesis warn that past performance is no guarantee of future results particularly as new pressures, like climate change, are changing the calculus. They note that many of the original treaties assumed stable river flows and static climates circumstances that no longer exist (Shabeh ul Hasson, 2012).

Conceptual Model

Figure 1 Climate change and cause of water Insecurity in South Asia

According to this model, the main cause of water insecurity in South Asia, especially in the Indus Basin that India and Pakistan share, is climate change. Floods and water scarcity are caused by monsoon unpredictability and glacial melt brought on by climate change. The Indus Waters Treaty (1960), which was not intended to handle contemporary issues like climate-induced variability or escalating geopolitical conflicts, intersects with these environmental stresses. Therefore, the danger of conflict between riparian states is increased by a combination of institutional flaws (outdated treaties) and environmental forces (scarcity and floods).

Hydro-Hegemony and Power Asymmetry

Related strand of scholarship focuses on the ways in which power inequity conditions transboundary water relationships. The theory of hydro- Hegemony, has been developed by Zeitoun and Warner ,2006 states that the dominant riparian country, that is, one of the riparian countries in a basin which want to control the development and management of the river and the people living along the river is at all times the strongest nation (often the upper riparian) (Ataev, N,2023). This power may be exercised by means of physical barriers or presence (dams, diversions, military deployments), or by institutional and discursive hegemony (influencing treaties, narratives, and norms to privilege its interests) (Martinez, 2024). Hydro-hegemony may generate non-war situations that are coercive: the weak riparian accepts an unfair deal because it has no alternative (Vasani,2024). Typically hailed examples include that of Egypt’s possession of the Nile (exercised in the current tussle with Ethiopia over dam construction), China’s leverage on the Mekong and the Brahmaputra in relation to its Southeast Asian neighbors and Turkey’s control of the headwaters of the Tigris-Euphrates. In such cases, the resident hegemon may not even need to shoot; it is the mere capacity to constrict flows that grants power (Yusupova, 2025). In South Asia, India is typically characterized as the regional hydro-

hegemon, particularly with respect to Pakistan and Bangladesh. India's upstream location on the Indus, Ganges, and Brahmaputra, and its relatively superior economic and military might make the country an effective water gatekeeper (The Diplomat, 2025). In fact, there have already been warnings from observers that India's recent actions on the Indus, including expediting dams and signaling possible treaty withdrawal, could be interpreted as a bid to secure its hydro-hegemony over Pakistan (Observer Bangladesh, 2025). The hydro-hegemony framework therefore allows an understanding that Indian actions are not tactical responses to security incidents but rather form part of a wider strategy to exploit rivers on which it shares sovereignty (Ganges Water Dispute, 2025).

Climate change and water security

Climate security literature intersects more with water conflict studies observing that global heating is a 'threat multiplier' in already vulnerable basins (Ali, 2024). Warming is projected to disturb the availability of water, making it scarcer in some regions and more abundant in others, causing more severe droughts in some areas, more recurring floods in others (Ahmed *et al*, 2025). The Himalayan glaciated reservoir of the Indus is already melting; in the short run this would lead to too much field water and flood whereas in the long run it would result in too little field water during dry seasons. Monsoon patterns in South Asia are growing equally erratic, some years too scanty in rainfall and others with overwhelming deluges (Gumman, 2025). Variability like this undermines the certainty of water guaranteed by old treaties. Analysts believe Pakistan, one of the world's most climate-vulnerable countries, will experience significant water scarcity in the years ahead. One study even suggests that Pakistan would face a 32% water deficit by 2025 based on demand (leading to a food production gap of tens of million tons) (Eisinger, 2025). This stark prediction highlights how climate change can drive a water-stressed, agrarian economy to crisis. Other policy events, such as the contributions of former UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon and UN Security Council debates, have also highlighted the role of climate-induced water scarcity in exacerbating conflict in the absence of cooperative adaptation (Sharma, 2024). That has, in turn, led to calls to update current water treaties to include climate adaptation measures such as flexible water-sharing formulas for drought years, joint drought-management plans, and data sharing on glacial melt and rainfall (Von Lossow, 2025). The Indus Waters Treaty, negotiated in 1960, contained no provisions for climate change (which, it is hardly necessary to say, had not been identified as a problem at the time). And here is the bigger-picture context: Some analysts contend that the So back to the bigger picture: Some analysts argue the IWT is therefore "outdated, in the climate era" it allocates waters inflexibly, by river, without any mechanism to respond to flows that are altering or to ecological needs (Eisinger, 2025). Given climatic changes and no renegotiation or at least technical cooperation, each country is apt to be forced to act unilaterally to increase the risk of conflict. The literature therefore also cautions that taking climate considerations into account when governing transboundary water is vital to avoid the breakdown of water sharing agreements under stress (Dawn, 2025).

Figure 2 Climate Change and water Security Challenges in South Asia

Figure 2.2 clearly demonstrates that It is becoming more widely acknowledged that conflict dynamics and water security are seriously threatened by climate change. The Himalayan glaciers are melting more quickly due to rising global temperatures, endangering the Indus Basin with both temporary floods and permanent water shortages. Instability is increased by irregular monsoon patterns, which result in years of droughts followed by devastating floods. Food security is at stake in Pakistan, which is already very sensitive to climate change, due to acute water scarcity and even a predicted 32% water shortfall by 2025, according to analysts. Older agreements, such as the 1960 Indus Waters Treaty, which had no provisions for climate adaptation, are being undermined by these changes. Calls for flexible treaty revisions, cooperative drought-management methods, and improved data-sharing on rainfall and glacial melt have resulted from the mounting strain. Both India and Pakistan run the risk of taking unilateral measures that could worsen regional tensions if they don't cooperate in adapting. In the end, preventing conflict and ensuring long-term water stability require incorporating climate issues into transboundary water administration.

International Law and Normative Frameworks

Figure 3 Framework of international laws

Finally, it is clear that some introduction of international legal principles is required since they constitute the context for assessing the potential weaponization of water by any state. At the foundations of treaty law lies the maxim pacta sunt servanda; treaties should be kept (Dawn Editorial, 2025). This is stipulated in the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties (1969), which explains that parties must execute treaties in good faith, and unilateral withdrawal is usually prohibited unless certain circumstances (such as a material breach by the other side) intervene. Article 60 of the Vienna Convention allows parties to suspend or terminate a treaty if there has been a material breach of the treaty by the other party, or under certain other extremely limited criteria (such as impossibility of performance, or a fundamental change of circumstances, the latter known as *rebus sic stantibus*) (Global Connectivities, 2025). Even *rebus sic stantibus* carries a significant burden – the new circumstances must be fundamental, unanticipated and that go to the core of the treaty’s very purpose. Statements of “fundamental change” in the context of water treaties, involving population growth and climate stress, are problematic, as these developments could largely be anticipated and were slow (Reuters, 2025). The Indus treaty provides that it shall not be suspended or terminated by either party except by an agreement between the two countries, indicating that unilateral suspension is against its terms and provisions (The Wire, 2025). In addition to treaty law, customary international water law – as evident from

the UN Watercourses Convention (1997) places upon all riparian states (including non-parties to any given treaty) the obligations of equitable and reasonable use of the shared watercourses and the duty not to cause significant harm to other riparian. What these principles imply is that in the absence of a treaty, an upstream country legally has no right to hoard the water or contaminate it, to the detriment of downstream countries. International institutions like the International Court of Justice (ICJ) (as in the case -the Gabcikovo-Nagymaros, Hungary and Slovakia-) have in earlier cases reaffirmed that a state cannot unilaterally withdraw from a water-sharing agreement on the pretext of domestic problems or general security reasons which are left vague; the only remedy is to seek a relief through mechanisms of dispute resolution (GAIHLH,2025). Furthermore, civilian resources and infrastructure are protected under international humanitarian law (like the Geneva Conventions), and intentionally depriving civilians of water during war (or peace) time is a crime. Though this is limited to armed conflict situations, it reflects a new norm developing around the prohibited use of water as a weapon of war or retribution (USIP, 2024). In summary, international norms are highly supportive of maintenance of water treaties and resolution of disputes through legal recourse, and characterise attempts to “weaponise” water as instances of unacceptable state behaviour. Much of the literature and conceptual framings reviewed here pave the way to understand how the logics are at work in the contemporary Indus Basin crisis (Gaeta,2025).

Methodological Description

Table 1 Methodological Description

Component	Details
1. Theoretical Foundations	- Hydro-hegemony framework - Securitization theory
2. Research Design	- Qualitative, theory-driven analysis - Case study method (Indus Waters Treaty, 1960 – present disputes)
3. Data Sources	- Primary: UN reports, policy pronouncements, treaties (Vienna Convention, UN Watercourses Convention) - Secondary: Academic papers, policy briefs, think tank reports (1990–2025)
4. Analytical Method	- Qualitative content analysis - Coding themes: weaponization of water, upstream hydro-politics, climate vulnerability, treaty renegotiation
5. Research Phases	Phase 1: Global-to-regional mapping (institutional conflicts, historical warnings, climate-security rhetoric) Phase 2: Indus Basin case study (Pakistan’s downstream vulnerabilities vs. India’s upstream strategies)
6. Outcomes	- Conceptually Driven Findings – Regionally Contextualized Insights – Analysis of How Water Securitization and Weaponization Influences Conflict Risks

Employing a qualitative research design, this study investigates the processes through which water is securitized and weaponized in international relations, with particular emphasis on the India-Pakistan conflict over the Indus Basin. The analysis is theory-driven, exploring how water shifts from being a shared natural resource to a strategic instrument of coercion and power, primarily through the lenses of hydro-hegemony and securitization theory. Adopting a case study approach, the paper centers on the 1960 Indus Waters Treaty and the contemporary disputes associated with it. This makes it possible to thoroughly examine how the conflict potential of transboundary water systems is shaped by unilateral actions, pressures brought on by climate change, and changing geopolitical dynamics. Primary sources for this study include official policy statements, UN reports, government communications, and international legal instruments such as the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties and the United Nations Watercourses Convention. These were complemented by a review of secondary literature, including scholarly articles, policy briefs, and think tank reports from 1990 to

2025, to capture both historical developments and emerging trends in water securitization. The materials were analyzed using qualitative content analysis, with coding focused on themes such as “water weaponization,” “upstream hydro-politics,” “climate vulnerability,” and “treaty renegotiation.”

The research was conducted in two phases. The first phase involved a global-to-regional mapping that highlighted institutional conflicts and historical warnings, situating the “water wars” discourse within the broader climate-security framework. The second phase operationalized these discussions through a detailed case study of the Indus Basin, examining Pakistan’s downstream vulnerabilities and India’s upstream control strategies. This two-tiered methodological approach ensures that the findings are theoretically grounded, analytically robust, and regionally contextualized.

Analytical Discussion

The Indus Waters Treaty in Retrospect

The 1960 Indus Waters Treaty (IWT) is often regarded as a landmark example of transboundary water cooperation. Facilitated by the World Bank following ten years of intense negotiations, the treaty offered a practical solution to water disputes arising from the 1947 partition of British India. It also divided the Indus Basin’s six rivers between the two new states: The three eastern rivers (Ravi, Beas, Sutlej) would be reserved for Indian use, while the more expansive western rivers (Indus mainstem, Jhelum, Chenab) would go to Pakistan. This arrangement, interestingly, appeared the second phase of the partition of the subcontinent. This was an enormous task involving huge expenses for the construction of alternate water courses as Pakistan had to surrender the eastern rivers. Imperatively, India did not politicized the IWT even during the wars of 1965, 1971, and 1999 against Pakistan. Both countries considered the treaty strictly institutional and depoliticized. IWT established bodies like the Permanent Indus Commission (PIC), comprising commissioners from both sides, which regularly shared information and conducted meetings to address IWT-related issues. IWT also provides a well-structured dispute resolution mechanism that comprises initial mutual discussions at the PIC, followed by adjudication from a Neutral Expert, and, if deemed necessary, the issue could be sent for arbitration or adjudication prompted by the World Bank. The most significant clause of the treaty is that it does not allow any of the parties to withdraw from the treaty unilaterally. Article XII (4) of the treaty says that it “shall continue in force until terminated by mutual agreement”, meaning either India or Pakistan can't walk away unilaterally. That binding nature was supposed to stop precisely what’s happening now: one party whimsically exiting the pact due to the whims of politics. World Bank and international lawyers have concluded that if India were to revoke the IWT, it would come into conflict with the terms of the accord as well as the general principles of International Law."

For more than six decades, IWT has essentially done what it set out to do. It provided for both India and Pakistan to develop their irrigation and hydropower potential with a minimum of outside interruption. Pakistan expanded what was already the world’s largest contiguous irrigation system in the Indus Basin; India built projects on its share of the rivers. Disputes did arise, to be sure - Pakistan has, for example, at times objected to Indian dam designs on the Jhelum or Chenab that it fears would allow upstream storage - but these were dealt with within the treaty's technical provisions, and with neutral expert adjudication (notably, such as over India's Tulbul Navigation project and the Kishanganga dam). World Peace: This lead to the East India Company to conclude five treaties of river water sharing while all other companies concluded only one. Govt of India under Nehru signed IWT in 1960 and it withstood all attempts to freeze its terms, showing that it had withstood Kashmir Wars of 1965 and 1971. The World Bank praised it as “one of the most successful international agreements” in water management. Security analysts observed that the IWT served as an unintended trust-building mechanism one of the few examples of institutional India-Pakistan cooperation that was insulated from the relationship’s broader fray. This makes the current situation that India has placed the treaty “in abeyance” even more distressing.

Pakistan’s Extreme Dependence and Vulnerability

Pakistan is one of the most water-stressed countries, which makes IWT extremely important for the country. The Indus River system is a lifeline for Pakistan’s economy, society and ecology. The basin comprises around 65 percent of Pakistan's land area and supports some 80 percent of its population. Almost all irrigated

agriculture in Pakistan, which in turn accounts for more than 90% of the country's food grain production, is dependent on Indus waters. Indus-stem irrigation supports roughly a quarter of Pakistan's gross domestic product, and nearly half of its employment. And those very rivers produce virtually all of Pakistan's electricity from hydroelectric dams, powering the lights for about 250 million people. In short, Pakistan's water security is national security: if the flow of the Indus were to dry up, the plains of Punjab and Sindh would "become a desert in a very short time," collapsing Pakistan's agriculture and causing widespread power shortages. Because of the lack of options this over-dependence is then further reinforced. Pakistan has scarce ground water (even that is being over-extracted), few large lakes and negligible precipitation outside the monsoon. Its water storage capacity is notoriously low current reservoirs are able to store only about 30 days' worth of river runoff, compared with about 900 days' storage capacity for a country the size of the United States, by one estimate. Consequently, Pakistan is highly vulnerable to disruptions in the timing of water flows: a weak dry season or a delayed monsoon can quickly result in water shortages and crop failures. Seasonal unpredictability is exacerbated by sudden shifts due to climate change. The devastating floods of 2022 and 2025, which submerged almost one-third of Pakistan, along with the prolonged drought in Sindh and Balochistan that continuously haunts people, are consequences of climate change. This situation further necessitates the importance of regulated water flow under the IWT (April 2025). Pakistan gets 90% of its food production and 80% of its irrigation water from the Indus River. Any disruption, even for a short duration, may cause a prolonged humanitarian crisis in the country. Because of this vulnerability, Pakistan perceives any threat to the Indus water as an existential threat to its existence. This urgency was reflected in Pakistan's response after the unilateral suspension of IWT by India after the Pahalgam incident. Pakistan firmly stated that any interference with IWT by India shall be treated as an act of war by Pakistan. India's unilateral suspension of the IWT shows its intent. Pakistan on the other hand, refuted this Indian move and stressed that IWT is still in force, where neither signatory of the two can unilaterally withdraw from it. The stakes of Pakistan are very high as far as the IWT is concerned. Any diversion of waters by the Indians after the abrogation of IWT shall be an act of killing 240 million Pakistanis without a bomb or missile. Pakistan is fully aware of this fact and which is why it declares that any such action on the part of India shall be considered as an act of war. This standoff between the two nuclear neighbours makes the water politics as dangerous as any nuclear war could be. It must be kept in mind that if the diversion of waters is left aside, only the flood-related regular information is vital for the survival of Pakistan. The recent floods of 2025 in Pakistan show that in the absence of mutual cooperation under the IWT, the denial of water-related information could also be catastrophic for Pakistan.

And a 10-20% reduction in water during a critical growing season would mean crop failure for millions of farmers, a spike in food prices and, most likely, the country needing to step up costly food imports or facing shortages. A larger, more lasting cut would be devastating: in a recent assessment of climate risks, it was reported that a 32 per cent shortage of water (which is plausible in the years ahead) would leave large parts of Pakistani farmland unusable and millions homeless. The prospect could trigger internal instability in the country, resulting in" large scale migration of rural population to urban areas, and increased poverty and unrest. In effect, Pakistan would be brought to the brink – effectively a "collapse" situation, with not a shot being fired – by a slow, gradual "implosion" caused by water-deprivation. That is why Pakistani leaders have vowed to "fight to the end" to safeguard their water source if they had to, even floating the prospect of a nuclear response if presented with a mortal threat to their water and, by extension, their state. Water securitization in Pakistan has progressed to the extent that now water security is indistinguishable from state security, and the Indus treaty is understood to be that last defence against catastrophe.

India's Upstream Leverage and the Suspension of Treaties as a Water Weaponization

India's April 2025 decision to unilaterally "suspend" the Indus Waters Treaty putting it temporarily "in abeyance," as New Delhi has put it — was a watershed (pun intended) in hydro-political relations. The immediate provocation was a horrific terrorist attack by militants in Indian-administered Kashmir (the Pahalgam carnage) killing 26 tourists that India holds was perpetrated by Pakistan-based extremists. Outrage was spreading through the public and Prime Minister Indian Narendra Modi and his government promised retribution. In a fiery speech, Modi said that "water and blood cannot flow together," connecting alleged Pakistani support of militancy to cooperation on sharing water. Soon after this, the Indian Foreign Secretary declared that India would place its IWT responsibilities in suspension till "Pakistan winds up cross-border

terrorism”. In such an unprecedented move that left Pakistan in shock, India suspended its participation in meetings of the Permanent Indus Commission and indicated that it can no more be bound by the restrictions on the exploitation of the waters of the western rivers. In essence, India dangled control of water as a stick a case of Indian water securitization, and an imagery that describes treaty obligations as dependent on positive security behavior of Pakistan.

Indian officials offered legal and pragmatic explanations for their action. They quoted the doctrine of *rebus sic stantibus* (fundamental change of circumstances), insisting that the reality in 2025 with a vastly increased population in India, much higher water demand and Pakistan allegedly using terrorism is a world apart from 1960 when the treaty was inked. Indian proponents of the abrogation of the IWT are of the opinion that India should not restrict itself to a treaty that is no longer pragmatic, as Indian water needs have increased manifold from what they were at the time of signing the IWT. They argue that increased demand for water at home has already made India a water-stressed country and by 2030, the demand for water shall be doubled as compared to the 2025 figures.

The Indus basin in India (mainly in the states of Jammu & Kashmir and Punjab) is but a small fraction of India’s total water resources, but every drop is becoming ever more precious with the Ganges and other rivers under pressure. For the nationalists, it was politically not good that India was letting 80% of the waters of Indus, just as promised by the treaty, to flow into Pakistan at a time when much of India was getting starved of water. Finding that the IWT hardly ever becomes the IGWT Hardline voices in India are calling the IWT “too generous” to Pakistan, and as a testament of past leaders’ idealism wanting an updation of the treaty. This sentiment was summed up by Indian home minister Amit Shah in June 2025 when he bluntly said, “The Indus Water Treaty will never be restored... Pakistan will be kept on a leash and it will be starved of water, which has been looted unjustifiably through the Indus treaty. The Indian intent is clear as they want to use water as a tool of arm-twisting against Pakistan for political and strategic leverage.

After suspension, India quickly tried to act on its upstream leverage. (In addition: Although reports surfaced that Prime Minister Modi had directed a fast track on dams, canals, and power projects on the Indus tributaries assigned to Pakistan, these were later confirmed by Reuters investigations. The reasoning was two-fold: one, India is allowed for some restricted non-consumptive use (such as hydropower, and small-scale irrigation) on the western rivers under the treaty; and two under the aggressively exploiting these allowances, India can enhance its water usage without technically violating the treaty more so if it claims the treaty is anyway in suspended animation. And secondly, by establishing faits accomplis on the ground (in the form of new diversion canals, for example), India strengthens its negotiating position if talks resume and gains the physical capacity to draw down flows. One prominent proposal includes double the size of the decades-old Ranbir Canal, built on the Chenab River, from 60 km to around 120 km in length. This would significantly increase India’s capacity to draw off water from the Chenab before it hits Pakistan to an estimated 150 cubic meters per second, in comparison with some 40 m³/s now. India has also expedited construction of hydroelectric projects including the Ujh dam (a tributary of the Ravi) and the second phase of the Kishanganga project (in the Jhelum). Most symbolically, the Uri-II hydroelectric dam built on the Indian side of Kashmir on the Jhelum River and opened in May 2025 siphoned off a river that enters Pakistan. On their own, any of these projects might not be game changers, but together they nudge India closer to a point where it could moderate, or even cut off, large parts of the water in the three western rivers. The Uri-II hydroelectric dam on the Jhelum River (Indian-administered Kashmir, May 2025) exemplifies India’s push to maximize upstream infrastructure on a river legally allocated to Pakistan under the Indus Waters Treaty. Since suspending aspects of the treaty, Indian authorities have accelerated the construction of such dams and expanded canal projects as part of a broader strategic approach. From the perspective of hydro-hegemony, India’s actions reflect the typical behavior of a dominant upstream riparian exercising its geographic advantage. India, ironically, is using water as a weapon against Pakistan, after alleging it for supporting cross-border insurgencies. This Indian mindset makes a clear case of lawfare against it, as it is trying to use the IWT for its strategic gains against Pakistan. In utter disregard for the humanitarian fallout of the abrogation of the treaty, India is using it as a leverage to pressurize Pakistan, even without credible evidence. Seemingly, India is creating a conflict situation, ridden with political purposes, instead of challenging Pakistan to an armed conflict.

In effect, this approach allows India to exert significant pressure while remaining below the threshold likely to provoke international condemnation or nuclear retaliation. Such water-based coercion can be more insidious than a direct military strike because it is gradual and can be masked with technical or legal justifications (for example, claiming routine maintenance or asserting entitlement to its share). Early indications of this strategy appeared in May 2025, when water levels at a key Chenab River point temporarily dropped by 90% during “maintenance” work on Indian dams affecting Pakistan. While India framed this as routine, the sudden drop alarmed Pakistani farmers and officials, signaling the potential for India to manipulate flows deliberately. Incidents like this underscore how control asymmetries translate into unequal risks—a hallmark of hydro-hegemony.

Legal and Ethical Considerations: Violation of Treaties and National Norms

India’s suspension of its obligations under the Indus Waters Treaty raises serious legal concerns. The treaty contains no provisions allowing unilateral withdrawal or suspension. By effectively placing its obligations “in abeyance,” India is, in practice, breaching the treaty unless it can justify such actions under international law. The argument that India appears to invoke is one of setting aside (or vitiating) the legal obligation in response (i.e. to Pakistan’s own alleged prior breach of failing to reign in (cross-border terrorism). Under international law, countermeasures are illegitimate actions a state may take in retaliation for another state’s unlawful act, with the purpose of inducing compliance. But the limits on counterattack are stringent: it must be proportionate to the original violation, and it may not violate [peremptory norms or basic humanitarian principles].” And even assuming *arguendo* that some obligation to India were breached by Pakistan’s purported complicity in a militant attack, freezing an entirely unrelated water treaty that can be breached, would put millions of people’s well-being and lives at risk, cannot be a proportionate or legal countermeasure. Independent legal experts point to the fact that the Indus Treaty was deliberately insulated from political and security disputes (as one analysis has it, “designed to operate irrespective of conflict”). So, using an idea of disputes on terrorism as a ground to suspend a water-sharing agreement is contrary to the treaty’s object and purpose. What’s more, deprivation of water can violate humanitarian law if it is directed at civilians, again as noted above. Another lens is that of the Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties: Article 62 (*rebus sic stantibus*), in theory, could permit treaty termination in response to a fundamental change in circumstances. But Pakistan and most neutral observers argue that things like population growth or variability of the climate, two of the reasons India has given, were mostly foreseeable or do not undermine the treaty’s basic terms long enough to set such a high bar. In fact, the treaty’s fundamental purpose — to share the Indus waters amicably may well be even more vital today, when it is under strain, than it was in 1960. And for good measure, the Convention’s Article 60 on termination of the treaty for material breach would not apply here either, because Pakistan has not violated the IWT itself; the terrorism element is extraneous to the treaty. For that reason, in strictly legal terms, India’s unilateral suspension is precarious. It contravenes the very letter of the IWT and is in opposition to the *pacta sunt servanda* norm. Pakistan maintains a firm legal position in asserting that India’s actions breach both treaty obligations and customary international law.

The country has multiple legal avenues to contest India’s maneuvers. Pakistan has already indicated its intention to invoke the dispute resolution mechanisms under the IWT, such as referring issues to a neutral expert or pursuing arbitration. However, this route is complicated by India’s lack of cooperation. Another option could be to approach the International Court of Justice, which would likely require India’s consent or a United Nations Security Council endorsement—both of which are challenging to secure. Pakistan could also appeal to the World Bank, a treaty guarantor and facilitator, to exert pressure on India. Historically, the World Bank only intervenes if both parties request its good offices, but Pakistan, with a vested interest in maintaining the treaty, could request diplomatic intervention. Furthermore, Pakistan could bring the matter before the United Nations Security Council, framing India’s actions as a threat to international peace and security. Although the UNSC has addressed water-related disputes indirectly in the past (such as resolutions concerning conflicts in Sudan), an India-Pakistan water conflict would attract attention from major powers, given both countries’ strategic importance. Yet, any UNSC action could face vetoes from India’s allies. On the international legal and reputational front, Pakistan emphasizes that India’s conduct violates global norms. Observers note that if India were allowed to breach a well-established water-sharing agreement without consequences, it could set a dangerous precedent for other upstream states Russia regarding Central Asian

rivers, China over the Mekong or Brahmaputra, and so on. Such a scenario would erode confidence in international water treaties. Therefore, the stakes extend beyond bilateral concerns to the integrity of international water law. The global community has a responsibility to prevent rivers from being weaponized. This principle underpins treaties like IWT and broader conventions: to remove water from zero-sum politics and manage it as a shared resource. There is also a humanitarian and legal dimension. Should India significantly reduce or seize control of the Indus flows to Pakistan, civilian populations would face severe threats to life and livelihood. Such action could amount to a crime against humanity if carried out deliberately and causing widespread suffering. While India has not yet executed such a cutoff—its actions remain threats—the mere potential exerts coercive pressure. Analysts have compared the scenario to a siege in warfare, where the attacker seeks to starve the population; in this case, the siege could target an entire nation. Geneva Conventions and Additional Protocols prohibit depriving civilians of sustenance as a method of warfare. Although at present there is no war-like situation between the two countries, and despite that, using the necessities such as water against Pakistan by the Indian side is utterly against the moral, ethical and international principles of peaceful co-existence. Even at times of war, the established agreements that are covered by international law and customary law are respected as they fall under the protection of civilians during the Law of Armed Conflicts. The Indian preponderance in this regard seems starkly against the established laws and cannot be justified under any emergency plea. These aspects of the IWT certainly come under international humanitarian law and therefore make a valid case for the intervention of international jurists and observers.

Order, Water, Nukes: Regional Stability and Broader Implications

The Indus standoff underscores a paradox in South Asian security. For decades, global attention on India and Pakistan has focused on their nuclear arsenals a justified concern given their history of near conflict. The logic of mutually assured destruction (MAD) is credited with preventing wars during crises such as the 1999 Kargil conflict or following the 2019 Pulwama incident, as conventional escalation could spiral into nuclear catastrophe. Nuclear weapons enforce discipline: their destructive potential deters large-scale conflict. Water has become a uniquely potent tool of coercion. Some analysts argue that India is exploiting a loophole in deterrence dynamics: Pakistan cannot respond militarily—or with nuclear retaliation against soft targets like dams or treaty violations without risking international condemnation. Consequently, India's water strategy inhabits a gray zone: deadlier than standard peacetime pressure yet remaining below open warfare thresholds. Water does not operate under the same deterrence framework that exists between India and Pakistan. Manipulation of water constitutes a form of aggression that remains below the MAD threshold. Unlike a sudden nuclear strike, river disruption causes delayed, cumulative damage failed harvests, depleted energy supplies, and economic strain rather than immediate destruction. Over time, this incremental impact can destabilize a nation more insidiously than conventional warfare. A nuclear event is catastrophic but instantaneous, creating a clear impetus for diplomacy or surrender. Water deprivation, conversely, can undermine a country gradually, triggering internal collapse or mass displacement without presenting a distinct *casus belli*. In Pakistan's context, abrupt Indus stoppages could imperil millions, while the responsible upstream actions might not provoke immediate military response.

Pakistan faces difficult choices. Inaction risks catastrophic drought; military retaliation could spark broader conflict that Pakistan seeks to avoid. Water weaponization, much like other force multipliers, introduces asymmetry even within a nuclear-deterrent equilibrium, one side can inflict substantial harm gradually while the other cannot reciprocate equivalently. The resulting strain could destabilize the victim state, potentially producing a failed state scenario with attendant nuclear and extremist risks. Unlike nuclear weapons, which deter sudden all-out war, water can facilitate a “death by a thousand cuts” strategy the Indus dispute exemplifies this dynamic. Beyond the resource itself, the conflict tests South Asia's peace architecture. Rising climate stress, coupled with strategic water manipulation, threatens to erode the longstanding taboo against direct conflict over shared rivers. Heightened rhetoric Indian officials threatening to “turn off the tap” and Pakistani leaders declaring such acts as war further inflames public sentiment. A government yielding under these pressures could face delegitimization, prompting military intervention and raising the risk of

escalation. Water, in this scenario, risks catalyzing the very conflict nuclear deterrence has historically prevented.

Towards De-securitization and Cooperative Water Governance

Conflict over water is not inevitable. The current Indus crisis has prompted calls from scholars, analysts, and mediators to resume dialogue and modernize the treaty rather than abandon it. Experts consistently note that the collapse of the IWT would harm both nations: Pakistan would face immediate water and food insecurity, while India could suffer reputational damage, sanctions, and regional instability. Maintaining the treaty aligns with India's self-interest: it guarantees safe use of the eastern rivers and access to a joint regulatory mechanism. Without it, India would face potential disputes across all Indus tributaries and threats to its own water projects. Analysts advocate for de-securitizing water in India-Pakistan relations, treating it as a shared economic resource rather than a national security issue. Confidence-building measures could include India sharing dam operation data and Pakistan curbing militant threats to water infrastructure. Investments in water efficiency would also reduce vulnerabilities: Pakistan could modernize irrigation through lined canals, drip irrigation, and less water-intensive crops, while India could complete and maintain its allocated canal projects to optimize usage.

Strengthening international norms is also crucial. India's non-participation in the UN Watercourses Convention complicates matters, but moral and diplomatic pressure remains. Pakistan's invocation of international law is not merely rhetorical; it highlights India's deviation from global standards. Broad international messaging emphasizing that water should not be weaponized could deter further unilateral actions. Trust-building measures, potentially involving backchannel diplomacy from neutral countries with stakes in South Asian stability, may be required to resume dialogue. Historical precedent is encouraging: even after high tensions, mechanisms like the PIC have successfully mediated disputes when political conditions allowed. Updating the IWT for climate realities is another forward-looking proposal. Potential improvements include: establishing joint real-time monitoring of glaciers and river flows; integrating environmental flow provisions to sustain ecosystems; creating protocols for droughts and floods (e.g., coordinated water releases during dry periods or upstream storage during floods); and empowering the Permanent Indus Commission, or a new joint body, to manage climate adaptation projects such as constructing storage dams with mutual technical support. Third-party mediation, possibly via the UN or World Bank, could provide neutral oversight and technical or financial support for cooperative infrastructure projects.

Conclusion

The recent crisis between India and Pakistan presented a new phenomenon in international politics where water has been weaponized for political or punitive purposes. This gave a credible leverage to the idea that water will be a securitized commodity in the 21st century. Looking at the importance of the IW for Pakistan, the upper riparian India has utilized its leverage to pressurize Pakistan in total disregard for the devastating effects that this action can bring to the people of the lower riparian Pakistan. Looking at the situation, it is safe to conclude that this water crisis has the potential to escalate into a much deeper crisis between the two nuclear rivals. Besides this, the current standoff between these two countries also points towards another important factor that, in the coming decades, water can be used for political purposes by countries with utter disregard for international law. Although IWT has the guarantee of the World Bank but despite that guarantee, the steadfastness of India reveals the weaknesses embedded in the fragility of the international system. If the international players, including the UN did not intervene to safeguard the IWT, these Indian footprints may cause further escalations in other parts of the world

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